

Talent Management and its Use in the Field of Human Resources Management in the Organization of the Czech Republic

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Abstract—The article is aimed at bringing information on the scope and the level of use of talent management by organizations in one of the Czech Republic regions, in the Moravian-Silesian Region. On the basis of data acquired by a questionnaire survey it has been found out that organizations in the above-mentioned region are implementing the system of talent management on a small scale: this approach is used by 3.8 % of organizations only that is 9 from 237 (100 %) of the approached respondents. The main reasons why this approach is not used is either that organizations have no knowledge of it or there is lack of financial and personnel resources. In the article recommendations suggested by the author can be found for a wider application of talent management in the Czech practice.

Keywords—Talent, talent management, use, mind map of talent management.

I. INTRODUCTION

IN the current business environment and in the conditions of competition and globalization increasing pressures, human resources are becoming for organizations a more and more pivotal factor. The main competitive advantage is not financial means, modern and efficient technology and technique or quality strategy but people, efficient employees. The importance of human resources in organizations was mentioned e.g. in study *'Aligned of the Top. How Business and HR Executives View Today's Most Significant People Challenges - and What They're Doing about It'* worked out by the Deloitte and Economist Intelligence Unit Companies in 2007 in which 85 % of respondents confirmed employees' fundamental influence on reaching the required efficiency of the organization [20]. Organizations that want to survive and expand, to outperform their present rivals and considerably increase their added value in such environment have to attract, cultivate and maintain talented employees - they have to pay attention to talent management. A number of talented individuals in the population are quite limited [7]. That is why the organizations should try to acquire those limited sources and use them as best as possible for themselves by the application of the most efficient instruments. The follow-up care of talented employees, the effort aimed at their development and retention in the organization should be also a matter of course.

In the Czech Republic the issue of limited number of competent people appears to be even more urgent as it is

accompanied by two current trends: aging of population and brain-drain. A number of talented people are attracted by the availability of opportunities to work abroad and/or by the offer to work for foreign firms being active on the Czech market.

In what way should then our organizations solve this problem? One thing they can do in this situation is to offer talented employees a real perspective, to change a strategy of their conducting. The present prevailing approach of using rather formal programs of talents development and focusing mainly on career management, succession planning or the creation of extraordinary groups of employees should be replaced by the system of talent management which will enable to talented individuals a real development and a deeper identification with the organization [12]. This system then will help organizations acquire and retain highly talented employees, build on their strong points, reward their success, provide them with a chance to make progress, and increase their overall efficiency.

A concept of talent management does not place any special demands on organizations from the standpoint of human resource management tasks as well as that of individual personnel activities. A careful application and mutual interconnection of the best principles and approaches that have proved their worthiness in practice, especially in the field of acquisition and selection, education and development, remuneration and care of employees are in question. Talent management does not concern, as it is sometimes mistakenly simplified, only a matter of remuneration and benefits for talented employees but also motivation, making advancement in their career possible, creation of appropriate working environment, their superiors' decent approach, cultivating a quality of recognition, appreciation and respect, the introduction of targeted strategies and others that will provide people and organizations with a space and the opportunity to develop and use their talent.

A prerequisite to the efficient working of talent management in the organization is its initiation and support by organizations' management and its interrelation with organization's business strategy. Particular processes of talent management then flow from this strategy and become a practical instrument of talented employees' management -

acquisition, development and retention of talents.

Talent management should not be aimed only at workers with a high potential, e.g. at managers holding top executive posts. It is necessary to introduce a broader approach that will identify talents and key segments of workers across the whole hierarchical organizations. Equally, talent management should not concentrate only on talents - individuals but also on the optimal involvement of talented people in teams and for the purpose of synergic effect then to form a sort of team total talent and that of the organization.

The approach of talent management use in human resources management has been carefully verified by the practice abroad, the organizations consider it as a useful instrument of systematic work with talented individuals. They really apply this system to the management of their human resources. As a proof, for example, can serve the results of the survey '2010 State of Talent Management' carried out by the world's biggest association of experts in the area of talent management New Talent Management Network in January 2010 [21]. The system of talent management has been implemented and is successfully used at 67 % respondents participating in the survey.

What is the situation, however, in the field of talent management use in human resources in the Czech business environment? Information on application of this approach within the whole Czech Republic or, for example, within a certain region does not exist. The author of the article thinks that the level of talent management application by the Czech organizations will be of rather minor extent. In order to confirm or refute this precondition and find out further information on talent management use, the survey of that approach to the application of human resources management in organizations in one of the Czech Republic regions, in the Moravian-Silesian Region, has been carried out. Evaluation and interpretation of data acquired by the survey can be found in the last part of this article.

The aim of the article is not only to describe the nature, significance, contributions and respective processes of talent management - acquisition, development and retention of talents, but especially to bring information on the use of talent management in human resources management in organizations of the Moravian-Silesian Region; as a fact it concerns the interpretation of data having been obtained by a questionnaire survey, mainly a confirmation or invalidation of hypothesis that talent management has been applied in less than 10 % of organizations in the Moravian-Silesian Region, and also a confirmation or invalidation of another hypothesis suggesting that the most often reason why talent management is not used in organizations of the Moravian-Silesian Region is the absence of its knowledge. The article is also aimed at submitting a thoughts map of talent management in the organization and at describing on that map based methodology of implementation and use of the given approach in the organization. The structure of the article corresponds with the requirements of fulfilling the set aim; in the introductory parts the basic concepts are defined, possibilities and benefits of

talent management are determined, the main part is then devoted to respective processes of talent management as a crucial part of talent management. In the last part of the article not only the contents, goals, method and the course of carried out questionnaire survey are described, the obtained findings are interpreted and the above-mentioned hypothesis are confirmed or invalidated but also recommendations for a broader application of this approach in the Czech practice can be found there. Description of the methodology of talent management's implementation and utilization in the organization and a reference to the thoughts map of this approach are also parts of the article. In the conclusion the most important facts of the whole text are summarized.

II. Specification of the Basic Concepts

A concept of talent and a concept of talent management rank among the basic concepts in the specified field. What is talent? Who can be labeled as a talent? What should be the idea of 'talent management' concept? To answer these basic questions, however, is not easy. Both at the academic ground and in practice the discussion of how to define a talent and how to determine talent management continues.

Some experts consider as a talent such an extraordinarily competent employee with a high potential who can significantly influence organization's performance and they think that talent management concerns only key individuals that is competent people heading for holding higher or top posts [10]. This attitude to who that may be labeled as a talent prevails also in this country, the Czech Republic.

Yet, some experts say that as a talent can be practically considered anybody who may contribute to the achievement of organization's goals that talent management should not be restricted to a few favored individuals only. To what extent an individual will contribute to the fulfillment of organization's tasks depends on the scope of attention the organization will pay to the development of their talent.

Katarína Smrčková from the PricewaterhouseCoopers Company says that in the Czech Republic we label as talents especially those who are expected to be appointed to managerial roles. There are, according to her opinion, our drawbacks in comparison with talent management abroad. For managers are not the only groups to be identified as talents. It also concerns specialists. For example, in the North Bohemia where it is difficult to find people to be employed in worker's positions, some workers who are able to lead and motivate others can be considered talents. According to that manager it would be probably good to demystify the word talent and its narrow perceiving only in relation to management [17].

Some authors describe a talent as an individual who is able to do differentiate 'his/her' organization from others, as an individual who to a significance extent influences organization's abilities to defeat competition [13].

One of the most common definitions describes a talented individual as a man who gives both a high performance and shows a high potential. Some organizations focus on the

ability to be promoted and as a talent they see only those employees who on the one hand give a high performance and they may be highly promoted on the other. On the contrary, other definitions focus on inputs or competences [4].

And how should be a concept of talent management defined? A prevailing part of the professional public agrees that the system in question is the system of acquisition, retention and development of talents.

Some experts consider as talent management the use of a mutually interconnected set of activities that are to ensure that the organization will attract, retain, motivate and develop abilities of talented people that it needs at present and will need in the future either [1]. The aim is to ensure a flow of talents and to realize that talents are the main resource of organization.

Also representatives of INC Consulting Joint Stock Company see talent management similarly. They state that the aim of talent management is to attract, develop, retain and take full use of employees with such skills and professional knowledge which will meet the current and the future needs of the firm [14].

Talent management includes several phases from scouting, selection, recruiting, appraisal, development, career planning, succession up to retention and socio-cultural and welfare activities for key employees who have already had some experience both from managerial and specialized roles and, subsequently, care of those who come immediately after leaving school [6].

BNET, a British server focused on the issues of management defines talent management as acquisition, choice, identification, retaining, management and development of employees about who are thought to have a potential for a high performance. According to that server, management of performance focuses on those individuals' skills and abilities, on their potential of growth, on the evaluation of their benefit to the success of organization.

The author of this paper considers a talent as an individual who brings both a high performance and shows a high potential; a mutually interconnected set of organization's activities whose task is to acquire, develop, motivate and retain talented employees needed for the fulfillment of both current and future business objectives she thinks talent management.

III. SIGNIFICANCE AND BENEFITS OF TALENT MANAGEMENT

In the life of organization a number of situations occur which as long as they are not solved have a negative impact on working of the organization, on the fulfillment of its business strategy, achieving a higher return on investments, work efficiency, productivity and the like. Successful managing of the issues of human resources management, their development, deployment and interconnection of their important knowledge appear to be a crucial field. This is and it will be crucial for the differentiation of prosperous organizations from others.

Not only theorists and representatives of foreign organizations but also representatives of Czech firms are beginning to realize that human resources are today more crucial than in any other time, they are beginning e.g. to understand the importance and advantages of work with talent as one of instruments of problematic situations solution, they are aware of its benefits for the organization [8].

There are several causes leading to the necessity of dealing with human resources, mainly then with talented individuals who influence performance and thus organization's competitiveness to a considerable extent - a permanent growth of specialization in all disciplines associated with a sharp growth of knowledge; the need of constant innovations, research and development; a limited flexibility of organizations to perform training 'on the scratch', which supports looking for required individuals among experienced employees on the labor market; lack of the right abilities (endemic problem of the most advanced industrial societies); at the time a low flexibility of workforce (from the reason of families having more careers, looking for a better balance between life and work, growing demands for requirements that should be met by 'ideal' work and others [4].

In the Financial Times of 2006 it was summarized: 'Talent is the most precious resource occurring in the today's modern world.'

By means of talent management, by means of systematic work with talents the following situations and strategic issues, for example, can be solved - the issue of identification and needs of talents in connection with trading priorities; difficulties with filling the most important positions appear in the organization, there is lack of skilled people on the market; a process of acquiring employees in the organization is successful but it turns out to be difficult to retain talented employees there; it is not possible efficiently to find talents and to identify employees with a high potential; it is difficult to look for a balance between a retention of employees in their positions and providing opportunities for their further development in the organization; in the organization there is a high fluctuation, mainly in the most important segments of workforce; 'best practice' programs have been implemented in the field but any significant changes cannot be seen in the approach to the employees; organization's customers pass from the organization to competition thanks to earlier personal relationships with former employees; it is expected that in the future a considerable organizational growth will occur or the acquisition requiring a presence of experienced employees will be materialized; restructuring initiated by organization's needs will happen and etc.

The main benefits resulting from a correctly set and applied system of talent management are as follows - talented employees contribute to a more considerable extent to the fulfillment of organization's strategy and economic goals; costs of fluctuation and acquirement of new employees drop; the organization becomes a sought after and attractive employer; talented employees are identified and retained; succession planning for key positions is more efficient as well

as ensuring of employees from the internal sources and their motivation; talented employees are appointed to appropriate positions and their potential is better used; losses connected with vacant key positions are minimized.

According to Forum talent management server, which is the first server concentrating solely on the issue of talent management and its impact on enterprise, talent management is worldwide the most topical theme of organizations' working and a priority matter for managers dealing with human resources management.

IV. PROCESSES OF TALENT MANAGEMENT

Talent management should be initiated and supported by a team of executives. According to study *'Have you got a sufficient number of talented workers? A key item on the management's agenda'* worked out by the Deloitte Company in 2008, this is one of key criteria in order to achieve a success in talent management [19]. Programs in the field of talents supported by the top management are usually more successful. By acting as an example, managers demonstrate a support and define what is important for their organization. The very implementation of talent management is then the competence of a manager who is engaged in the field of human resources. It stands to reason that cooperation of their subordinates and experts in information technologies is necessary. In big organizations external consultants take part in the whole process while managers in small firms rely on internal employees only if the whole process is to be ensured.

The efficient work with talents is based on building talent management strategy that will be in line with organization's philosophy and business strategy. Only from that strategy and through the strategy of human resources management key decisions can originate suggesting whether and which activities of talent management should be implemented. Strategy of talent management is aimed at ensuring a fund of highly talented, competent, committed and loyal individuals able to contribute to achieving the current as well as future organization's requirements, a so-called talent-pool.

Three basic groups of processes leading to ensuring an adequate talent pool is a practical outcome of talent management strategy. It is acquisition, development and retention of talents. Each of these processes includes in itself a whole number of related activities, a number of particular elements.

Talent management will be successful only on condition that it is connected with the internal and external recruitment, educating and development of talents, their rewarding, evaluation, motivation, leadership and internal communication. It is necessary clearly to define and communicate within the organization according to what criteria the talents are chosen, who will be a guarantor of their program and who and how will take care for the talents. It is very important to plan what programs will be offered to the talents before the choice of participants in the program, under what conditions and time intervals the projects will be

assigned to them or when and under what circumstances they will pass over to the subsequent positions.

It is apparent that talent management consists of a wide range of areas, from a quite a number of activities. Organizations differ in ways of how they manage their talents [1]. The ideal approach is to interlink all activities or at least most of them, which is what some organizations are really striving for. Some firms, however, concentrate on one or two activities only, which is not the idea of a systematic approach to talent management.

A. Talents Acquisition

The first step the organization has to take is to identify key roles. These are such positions in the organization which, if they are not filled, may seriously disturb working of the organization as these roles are the most critical for achieving its success. In connection with that the organization has to assess whether there are available employees with key competencies who will be needed in the future in dependency with business strategy. As long as it has not sufficient existing resources then it has to find these talents. It may identify them among its present employees, from the internal resources or obtain them from the external resources, among students, graduates, among employees who have got research fellowship in the organization, by transferring of talents from competitive or supplier firms, by means of the Internet, by use of headhunters and the like.

Organizations should realize that to have a success in the field of talent management is not mainly based on how many talents and what talents they have acquire in competition with other organizations, but mainly how they will be dealing with talents they have already got, how they will motivate and develop them and in what way they will take care for them and whether they will respect them, and to what extent they will retain them [7].

According to the study *'Have you got a sufficient number of talented workers? A key item on the management's agenda'* worked out by the Deloitte Company in 2008, organizations take an interest in the identification of talents [19]. This is the most developed field of talent management and at the same time field in which organizations feel most confident.

In addition to the above described two activities - the identification of key roles and defining the need of talents, the whole process of talent acquisition consists of three basic steps: 1 - the identification of key competences and creation of a rating scale to specify talents' contributions to the organization, 2 - performance appraisal and a potential prediction, and the creation of measuring scales for their measurement, 3 - the creation of a talent-pool.

An important step that the organization has to take in talent management is to identify key competences of the organization, which are competences crucial for the success of every employee and thus of the whole organization. Key competences are the combination of factors leading to ensuring of organization's constant success on the market, to its differentiation from competitors. Specification of

competences enables organizations to identify in which direction the talent of individual employees should be formed so that it can bring a benefit for the organization and at the same it makes possible better to measure to what extent the set expectations are fulfilled.

The maximum 30 key competences exist and that majority of organizations employs in talent management something between nine and eleven competences [3]. Orientation to activity, communication, creativity and critical judgment, orientation to a customer, interpersonal skills, leadership, team work or technical/functional qualifications they consider as nine representative key competences.

For example, key competences that were used for the identification of talents in a concrete real organization (HSBC Bank) are described in this way: orientation to trade and brand (prospective thinking, strategic thinking, the ability to innovate and the implementation of changes), concentration on the market (decision-making, spirit of enterprise, business thinking), leadership (concentration on activity, inspiring others, development of others), orientation to a customer (acquiring new customers, promotion of the orientation to a customer), cooperation with others (building relationships, the art of listening to others, the ability to exert some influence, information sharing, promotion of open communication), orientation to own development (the ability to learn, orientation to team's objectives, flexibility) [9].

Every competence has to be described and judged (by assigning a certain number of points) in the dependency on its relative contribution to the organization (see Table I).

In the given example, numbers from 1 to 6 are assigned to the described levels of communication according to their contributions to the organization. Such scale has to be constructed for each competence. Similarly, the minimum level of competence necessary for doing certain work has to be specified for each position in the organization.

In the Table II it is then possible to find the application of rating scales of all key competences for various positions in the organization, a so-called competence grid. In this competence grid every position in the organization is assessed according to a rating scale on the basis of necessary contribution to the organization required by the specified position. For example, as a contribution of organization's managing director is the highest, this position has got the highest rating in all competences.

After that key competences are determined and defined, performance appraisal and a prediction of individuals' potential follow. Performance appraisal is the measurement of actually achieved results within those areas for which the specified individual is responsible, and/or competencies understood as critical for the success of performed work as well as of the entire organization. A measuring scale most often used in organizations is as follows: considerably exceeds

TABLE I
RATING SCALE FOR A 'COMMUNICATION' COMPETENCE

	1	2	3	4	5	6
Definition of 'communication': He/she is able to communicate well both verbally and in writing. He/she efficiently communicates information and ideas to others, listens to them carefully and understands various standpoints. He/she informs on their ideas clearly and aptly, he/she is able to grasp details of presented information.						
	He/she expresses their wishes and needs clearly and appropriately.	He/she has good abilities in verbal and written communication, he/she knows how to listen to others.	He/she knows how to adjust their communication to the needs of listeners so that communicated information can be optimally understood.	He/she presents information and ideas in an active way and encourages others to do the same.	He/she encourages people to speak their mind, to express their ideas, he/she encourages communication without negative feedback.	He/she is considered as somebody who efficiently explains and communicates key/strategic information.

Source: L. A. Berger, D. R. Berger, "Talent Management Handbook: Creating Organizational Excellence by Identifying, Developing & Promoting Your Best People," New York: McGraw-Hill, 2003.

expectations (5), exceeds expectations (4), comes up to organization's expectations (3), below expectations (2), deep below expectations (1).

TABLE II
A COMPETENCE GRID

Competence	Position						
	General manager	Manager of finance	HR manager	R&D director	Operational manager	Salesman	Officer
Orientation to activity	6	5	5	5	4	3	1
Communication	6	6	6	5	4	3	1
Creativity/ability of innovation	6	6	5	6	4	2	1
Critical judgment	6	6	6	5	4	2	1
Orientation to a customer	6	5	5	5	4	3	1
Interpersonal skills	6	5	6	5	4	3	1
Leadership	6	6	5	5	4	2	1
Team work	6	6	6	5	4	2	1
Technical/functional qualifications	6	6	6	5	4	3	1

Source: L. A. Berger, D. R. Berger, "Talent Management Handbook: Creating Organizational Excellence by Identifying, Developing & Promoting Your Best People," New York: McGraw-Hill, 2003.

Prediction of a potential is in fact a prognosis by how many levels within the organization an employee can advance on the basis of their past/current performance appraisal, training and development, preferences in their careers, and the current and planned levels of competencies. A scale most often used by organizations is as follows: a high potential (5) → it is possible to promote by two levels or even more, a higher potential (4) → it is possible to promote by maximum two levels, an average potential (3) → it is possible to promote by one level, a limited potential (2) → ready for a lateral redeployment, no potential (1) → it is not possible to promote at the moment.

Key competences which are the basis of performance appraisal and predictions of the current employees' potential and thus the basis of acquiring talents from the internal resources may be used in the process of talents acquisition from the external resources. While the measuring scale for a potential forecast may remain unchanged (see above), the measuring scale for performance appraisal should be adjusted in the following way: considerably exceeds other candidates (5), exceeds other candidates (4), equals other candidates (3), below the level of other candidates (2), far below the level of other candidates (1).

Of course, a choice of the measuring scales type (or of one aggregate scale only) always depends on a concrete organization. As it is mentioned, e.g. in the study *'Have you got a sufficient number of talented workers? A key item on the management's agenda'*, worked out by the Deloitte Company in 2008, one of the approached organizations (operating in tourism and catering services) is using on the basis of performance appraisal and the forecast of a potential just one aggregate scale by means of which it divides its employees into seven categories [19]. According to those categories it tries to specify its talent-pool. They are as follows: leadership - 'readiness to accept more than one role', 'ambitious managers aspiring for a higher position', 'respected executives', and using of skills - 'ready to improve themselves', 'workers with good results', 'skilled workers', and 'excellent experts'.

There are a number of methods the organization can use for performance appraisal and a forecast of employees' potential both from the internal and external sources i.e. methods serving to the identification of talents. For a certain type of employee it is always necessary to choose such kinds and combinations that would lead both to performance appraisal and a forecast of potential. It is not possible to rely on one method only.

Talents from own sources are usually sought for through a working system of regular appraisal within which a number of methods are utilized. To the most used methods belong the method of assessment according to set objectives (MBO - Management by Objectives), assessment centre, the analysis of critical events, and a 360° feedback. In order to identify talents from the external sources the tests of fitness, a method

of assessment centre and behavioral (competent) talks can be used.

According to the study *'Have you got a sufficient number of talented workers? A key item on the management's agenda'* worked out by the Deloitte Company in 2008, almost 80 % of organizations identify talents through a regular assessment, in 60 % of organizations there are line managers who nominate employees into a talent-pool on the basis of having interviews with them, and in 40 % of organizations assessment centers are used [19]. It depends on a concrete organization which procedure for the identification of talents it chooses.

Outcomes of performance appraisal as well as a potential forecast have to be recorded (see Table III).

TABLE III
 PERFORMANCE APPRAISAL AND FORECAST OF A POTENTIAL

Evaluators: Jan Novák		
Evaluated: Karel Černý		
Key competence	Potential: 1 Point score	Total performance: 2 Appraisal of performance at the current position
Orientation to activity	2	below expectations
Communication	1	deep below expectations
Creativity/innovation	2	below expectations
Critical judgment	2	below expectations
Orientation to a customer	3	meets expectations
Interpersonal skills	3	meets expectations
Leadership	3	meets expectations
Team work	3	meets expectations
Technical/functional qualification	1	deep below expectations
Total	20	

Source: L. A. Berger, D. R. Berger, "Talent Management Handbook: Creating Organizational Excellence by Identifying, Developing & Promoting Your Best People," New York: McGraw-Hill, 2003.

After performance appraisal and a potential prediction, the very group of talented employees is identified - a talent-pool is being shaped. Individuals meeting in advance determined criteria (e.g. performance has to be evaluated as such which exceeds expectations (5) or considerably exceeds expectations (4), or meets expectations, and a potential has to be predicted as high (5), or higher (4), or average (3) and it can be jointly indicated as talents or this group of talented individuals can be furthermore divided into three groups - top talents, talents and potential talents. This situation is represented graphically in the Table IV by means of a so-called classification grid.

It always depends on the organization which way it will choose in approaching talents' classification. For example, the GE Company looking for talents in the whole organization on the basis of regular appraisal divides its employees into three categories: talents represent 20 %, quality working employees 70 %, and the remaining 10 % are those whose performance does not meet organization's demands [2]. Equally, the decision whether only talents or top talents or talents or all three groups will be included into programs for talents depends on the organization.

TABLE IV
 CLASSIFICATION GRID OF TALENTS

		Performance				
		low			high	
		(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
low	(1)					
	(2)				possible talent	
Potential	(3)			possible talent	possible talent	talent
	(4)		possible talent	possible talent	talent	top talent
high	(5)			talent	top talent	top talent

Source: L. A. Berger, D. R. Berger, "Talent Management Handbook: Creating Organizational Excellence by Identifying, Developing & Promoting Your Best People," New York: McGraw-Hill, 2003.

If we simultaneously consider the level of performance and that of potential in relation to a possibility of talent promotion, then we can describe it in the following way: potential (5) and performance (5) → it is possible to promote by more than two levels or even more, potential (5) and performance (4) or potential (4) and performance (5) → it is possible to promote by maximum two levels, potential (5) and performance (3) or potential (4) and performance (4) or potential (3) and performance (5) → it is possible to promote by one level, potential (4) and performance (2) or potential (4) and performance (3) or potential (3) and performance (3) or potential (3) and performance (4) or potential (2) and performance (4) → ready for a lateral redeployment.

In connection with the creation of talent-pool the management of the company should clearly show that anybody may become a talent if he or she will meet in advance set criteria. A program for talents should be set as motivating not only for its existing participants but also for potential participants. Talents should soundly compete to obtain their place in the program and they should be clearly acquainted with the fact that if they stop to meet the required criteria, somebody else may be nominated to their place in the program. On the basis of the study *'Magnet for Talents: Approach to Talent Management in the Czech and Slovak Republic'* worked out by the Deloitte Company in 2006, it is beneficial if talents in the company are respected as the 'elite', however it is important to communicate that the 'elite' in question is not 'the elite whose posts have been already secured' but that anybody may become a member of such elite [18].

B. Talents Development

Another important area which the organization has to focus on is the development of talented individuals. The organization should take for the identification of talents? It should be ensured that these people will stay and do not leave the organization for various reasons. A demanding work

should be offered them, an opportunity of further development, and acquiring of abilities required for their work in more complex job positions. Talents should be promoted and rewarded by means of incentive programs they should get a possibility of working at special projects that will enable them to show their qualities.

The organization should offer those individuals a possibility of their strong points development, the improvement of individual total performance as well as of particular competences, strengthening their motivation and making the development of their career possible. For talented employees, a special development plan should be materialized in a close cooperation with their managers that should have a shape of the integral program for the exactly specified group of talents supplemented by particular participants' individual needs. This program should be a superstructure of the usual development offer and individual care that talented employees should usually receive from the line management as well from human resources management As concerns the length of those programs, long-term training programs are not recommended in the current quickly changing world, return on investments invested into the programs is less probable for the reason of employees' difficult retention and shortening the length of being with the same organization. That is why organizations prefer shorter but well drawn up programs relevant to their needs for which the return on investments is supposed to be prompter.

And what is the shape of such development program? It may include a combination of various methods, activities or instruments of talents development but always according to the specific needs of the concrete organization. The methods employed are both the methods used to the development at a workplace at job performance (on-the-job) and the methods used to the development outside a workplace (off-the-job). A greater emphasis is laid on methods used for education at a workplace but, of course, both groups of methods are used. To the methods on-the-job belong coaching, mentoring, the assignment of a task, job rotation (cross training), work at projects, research fellowships, and the like. Methods of off-the-job include lectures, seminars, case studies solutions, workshops, managerial games, development centre, outdoor training/learning, e-learning and others.

According to the Deloitte Company's survey and the experience from international companies that have already applied talent management, the most efficient way of talent development are methods of on-the-job or learning directly at a workplace, mainly cross-training and the involvement in projects with the support of a manager, coach or mentor. This way of development interlinks learning at projects inside a concrete organization and within the framework of the team by means of social bonds that are efficient in the firm. A talent at the same time acquires a feedback from others and in this way he/she can better identify themselves with the firm. A considerable emphasis is put on coaching as an instrument of self-reflection, understanding oneself, of oneself possibilities and limits, formulating of ambitious but feasible goals, plans,

expectations and finding of optimal ways to their materialization - consequently to the change of thinking, attitudes, behavior and acting towards the effective enhancement of own performance as well as that of others.

Programs of talent development are very closely connected with carrier management that is with career planning and succession planning. They provide talents with opportunities to grow in their current job roles and to move forward to the roles of a higher level. Career planning shapes the advancement of talents in the organization in compliance with the judgment of organizations' needs. Talented people should go through a certain sequence of experience supplemented by coaching and development programs that will prepare them to be ready to occupy more demanding job roles in the future. Succession planning is to ensure that the organization will have to its disposal talents that it will need to satisfy its business needs in the future. The results of succession planning are plans of succession, most often in key roles.

For career management it is important that employees get opportunities of advancing in their positions and of their career development; in this way it is ensured for the organization to have a supply of such talents which it needs [1].

Career management in the field of talent management is closely connected with employees' performance appraisal in the way as it works e.g. in the Merk CZ Company. Hana Musilová, a manager of human resources in this organization describes that from their company's vision followed a necessity of interconnection between talent management and succession planning, and performance management. That is why the organization started to work on their implementation simultaneously. According to Musilová's opinion, this is a cyclic process taking place every year with intensive cooperation of line managers. It is just by them suggested nomination that brings potential talents in the light. Potential talents who will subsequently receive a positive appraisal as a result of standardized assessment procedures they have undergone will acquire a primary succession to the key positions in the organization [16].

Unfortunately, as Kejhová states, there are firms in the Czech Republic that mostly look for a good successor as late as the critical moment arises, it cannot be said that they would approach work with talents systematically and conceptually. Even though they implement programs of succession it can sometimes happen that these programs fail. As Stanislav Háša, a consultant from Deloitte Company mentions successors have a tendency to leave the organization. From surveys it is obvious that sixty percent of successors will leave the corporation in spite of having got a promise that in the course of time they will get a higher position. According to Háša, the problem rests in the fact that organizations promise to people they will train them as successors; if this is not fulfilled and those people are all the time only waiting, then they will prefer accepting an opportunity somewhere else. In his opinion a trend according to which one person was trained for a concrete chair is not in effect any more. That is why broadly

educated experts who are able quickly to cope with work load at any managerial post are preferred nowadays.

Approach to this problem is different abroad. The best workers who the organization relies on and intends to promote or appoint them to executive positions are really conducted and controlled according to a so-called career plan or a succession plan. Martin Heger, the executive with Heger&Partner consulting company says it works in such way that the head of the company does not know in advance who will be his substitute, at least two or three substitutes are mostly trained within a training or rotary program. He/she who is best trained is nominated for a new role if the right time comes. If they prove their ability they stay if not then their substitute comes. The program lasts from eight months to two and half a year. In the world this is a quite common model, in this country it is put into practice mainly by foreign companies [15].

C. Talents Retention

Also activities ensuring retention and stabilization of talents in the organization are inseparable part of talent management. The aim is to ensure that talented employees stay in the organization as its devoted members and in their work engaged people that they do not have a tendency to leave because their departures have usually extraordinary impact on organization's operation, which is irrelevant to their number.

If the organization wants people to work there, it should be respected as an organization which reaches good results, its behavior is ethical and it can offer its workers good conditions, it has a clear vision, and a set of interrelated and working values as an organization having a good reputation.

The organization should do its best to be 'an attractive employer', to be a place where people like to work, 'an excellent workplace', and 'an excellent place for work performing'. Among factors contributing for the organization to be an attractive employer there is the offer of interesting and valued work, providing the opportunity to learning and development and advancement in career for talents, respecting a balance between the life at work and a private life by the organization, the offer of a flexible role to talented employees, the offer of quality work conditions and equipment, providing a feeling of recognition and respect, the offer of an adequate reward, and recently also promotion of organization's responsibility to the society. On the part of the organization it is a so-called defensive approach based on the idea that as long as the work environment is for talents as attractive as possible, their tendency to leave the organization will be smaller [11]. The opposite is a so-called retaliation approach; organizations make steps to threaten the out-coming employees or the organizations receiving them or they harmed them in some way. This is e.g. enforcement of clauses concerning the ban on competition, lodging complaints against organizations trying to win employees over to their side, winning the employees over of those organizations and etc.

To the three factors that influence retention of talented

employees in the organization most of all, the opportunity of advancement in their career, the offer of interesting and satisfaction bringing work, and ensuring opportunities to training and development can be ranked [5]. Findings resulting from the research carried out in 2009 by the Pan European HR Network Company by the method of a structured interview with 200 managers at all levels in organizations involved in various branches all over the world.

The above-mentioned facts create for a talented individual a valuable offer marking that sound values will be observed in the organization, employees can expect good leadership, freedom and autonomy, highly incentive work, opportunities for professional advancement in their career and adequate remuneration [1]. It is necessary to ensure that talented individuals would be aware of being appreciated and that they have a considerable or even a principal value for the organization.

It is worth mentioning that on the basis of the analysis of organizations that appear every year on the ranking list of 100 Best Companies to Work for published in the Fortune Journal, the following positive indicators which successful organizations have in common have been indicated: executives pay attention to what employees say, a balance between a life at work and a private one is really respected, culture of long hours at work is rejected, flexible forms of work are used as long as it is possible, employees are seen as trustworthy persons, managers are given for them significant tasks, employees are asked what training they would welcome, their transmittable skills are improved.

The following control list of questions can serve as an instrument by which organization's leadership may find out whether the organization is seen as 'an attractive employer': How is our organization seen from outside? How is it seen by our customers? Are possible employees familiar with the name of our organization? How well do we know needs and interests of our target talents? Is there any geographical dissimilarity? Is there any dissimilarity in dependency on sex? Is there any dissimilarity in dependency on the age? Are customers' values in relation to our brand clearly defined? What words, what expressions might our critics connect with our brand? What could our patron say? As regards the brand, are our values identical with those of our employees? Is there any discrepancy? Does a mutual positive relationship with our key values exist? Do we focus our employment brand on various segments? How good are we at concentration on various segments? Is a psychological agreement in balance - i.e. is it beneficial both for the organization and the employees? Are we one of the organizations appearing on some ranking list of the best organizations? Are we a holder of a certification Investor in People? Have we been nominated for awarding a prize of outstanding employer? [4].

Another aid for the evaluation of organization's reputation can be considering negative indicators that are (similarly as positive indicators) published every year as part of the ranking list of 100 Best Companies to Work for in the Fortune Journal. The indicators are as follows: high fluctuation, high

absenteeism, a high level of stress, too many of long meetings, difficulties in making decision, atmosphere of politicking, lack of efficient communication, people are in fear of going to work, in a wrong way communicated organizations' values and the indistinct organizational structure.

Another instrument which can be employed in the evaluation of organization's reputation is to ask its employees a question whether they see their organization as the 'employer of a high quality'. The employees will response to 27 statements, they will evaluate whether they agree with them or not by applying a following rating scale: 4 = I very much agree, 3 = I agree, 2 = I do not agree, 1 = I very much disagree. The statements are e.g. as follows: By and large my work stimulates me. My work is sufficiently responsible for me. My work enables me to use my skills. I clearly understand what I am expected to at my work. Amount of work I have to perform is reasonable. I can keep a reasonable balance between my work and other obligations in my life. Quality enhancement is part of my routine work. I am motivated in my work for the organization. I have got adequate freedom of being able to reach my goals and the like.

Results of the survey should be subsequently evaluated and a discussion with employees should take place that would make their opinions clear, they should get an opportunity to express or, as the case may be, to suggest a solution leading to the improvement of the situation. As a variant, a 180° method can be used by means of which the leadership reacts to the above-mentioned statements; their answers are then compared with employees' evaluation.

Information about areas which are not satisfactory from the standpoint of retention and stabilization of talents may be provided by outgoing employees, by interviews with them or it can be obtained from questionnaire surveys performed among them. We can ask the outgoing employees these questions: Why have you decided to leave? Why did you want to find a new employer? What a new employer has offered you? What would persuade you to stay? What reason for your leaving our organization did you tell a person who ran a job interview at your current employer? What reason of your leaving our organization did you tell your former executive? What were negative aspects of work in our organization? Did your former executive meet your expectations taking into consideration everyday management, opportunities to development and motivation? Did you get a fair reward for your work done in our organization? Did our organization give you opportunities and resources for training and development about which you were sure you needed them? Did any barriers exist in our organization preventing you from development? Was our organization able to satisfy your career effort? Were working conditions in our organization satisfactory? Did they come up to your expectations? Has your departure influenced in some way relationships at your workplace?

All gathered information, both the evaluation from the view of leadership and the current and former employees' opinions of organization's reputation should be carefully analyzed,

weighed, and related to processes of human resources management in the organization. Then, proposals and recommendations how to improve organizations' reputation should be submitted i.e. how to ensure a better retention (but also acquisition) of talented individuals.

Consequently, the organization should focus on a proposal of such activities that would put a limit on or prevent talented workers from leaving. In dependency on the result of the analysis of obtained information and on overall judgment of reasons for talented individuals or their groups leaving, the organization should take an interest in the systems of remuneration that are not competitive, they are not unjust and unbiased [1]. It is necessary to realize that not only financial means are in question; talents should be offered also other forms of rewards - interesting work, relevant way of acting and the like. Tasks and job opportunities in the organization should be created in such way so that a variety of work, the importance of tasks, autonomy, checking of own work, and feedback could be ensured. Also the opportunity of education, growth and career advancement should be ensured. Some roles can be 'made-to-measure' and thus accommodate concrete individuals' needs. The organization should do its best in order to ensure loyalty to work not only by creating work tasks and job opportunities, but also by work organization in connection with projects the talents can identify with better than with the organization as a whole. By using these methods, building of social bonds should be encouraged in the organization, decisions on the choice or professional advancement should be properly made so that individuals' abilities could be duly interconnected with requirements of work which is to be performed by those people. Furthermore, the organization should try, in connection with preventing talented employees from leaving, its employees in the period after joining-up the organization will be able to adapt themselves to their work, team, and the organization as best as possible. In the starting phases of their work for the organization they should be offered the appropriate assistance, education and training. The organization should put into effect activities that will lead to the improvement of balance between a life at work and extra-work life. This includes e.g. a chance of flexible work regime or flexible ways of employment respecting extra-work needs of talented individuals. Unfavorable work conditions should be eliminated and excessive occupational stress should be removed or made lower. The organization should choose, inform and train managers and heads of teams in such way that they are aware of positive contribution by which they can contribute to better retention of talents. However, they have to choose the right way of managing their teams.

Therefore, it is necessary to concentrate on all areas in which a lack of loyalty and a talents' growing dissatisfaction might appear. If insufficient attention is paid to areas influencing retention and stabilization of talents then, as a result, talented employees might leave the organization, which would certainly influence its working in a negative way.

V. MATERIAL AND METHODOLOGY

To confirm or refute the assumption of a rather lower level of talent management use by Czech organizations and also to find out further information on all aspects of this approach application in practice, a survey of talent management use in one of Czech Republic regions, in organizations of the Moravian-Silesian Region has been carried out. The author assumes that the level resulting from the survey having been carried out in that region might be roughly analogous also in other regions of the Czech Republic with the exception of the capital of Prague area, and probably also the area of the Central Bohemia Region. The author expressed this hypothesis on the basis of experience with carrying out a similar survey the purpose of which was to find out to what extent Czech organization used the method of assessment centre⁹. Of course, to obtain a comprehensive view of the issue of talent management use, the survey would have to be carried out in organizations within the whole Czech Republic at best or as a supplement of already carried out survey in organizations of the Moravian-Silesian Region, in the capital of Prague and in the Central Bohemia Region.

This would be, however, a more extensive investigation and that is why the author focused on one region only. Survey in organizations of the Moravian-Silesian Region can be understood as a pilot one to a comprehensive survey which the author will realize as an independent activity.

The whole process of the survey took place in four basic phases: 1 - survey (definition of survey content, specification of survey goals, formulation of hypothesis, choice of method (s) of survey, realization of own survey), 2 - data processing, 3 - interpretation of findings, 4 - recommendations for practice.

A. Survey of Talent Management Use in Organizations of the Moravian-Silesian Region

The content of the survey was to map the issue of talent management use in human resources management in organizations of the Moravian-Silesian Region.

The aim of the survey in particular organizations was to find out not only the extent, content, importance and benefits of talent management use but also interested persons' response to the implementation and use of talent management, causes why talent management was not used or used unsuccessfully in its application, kinds of instruments applied to particular regions of human resources management (job performance assessment, development and education, motivation and retention of employees, career management) and the impact of the current economic crisis on the use of talent management.

Hypothesis that were to be confirmed or invalidated by the survey were formulated like this: Hypothesis A - Talent management is used by less than 10 % of organizations in the Moravian-Silesian Region, and Hypothesis B - The most often cause why talent management is not used by organizations of the Moravian-Silesian Region is the fact there is the absence of its knowledge.

As a method of survey the electronic inquiring was chosen

by means of in advance formulated questionnaire the part of which was also a covering letter. In the covering letter the nature of talent management as a comprehensive and systematic approach to managing talented individuals including both activities of talent individuals acquisition, their development and retention in the organization. Therefore, the organizations taking part in the survey knew exactly what the contents of talent management was and so it could not happen that even though they used talent management they would answer the question concerning using or not using that approach in a negative way. The questionnaire included a total of 25 questions, 20 of them concerned the solved issues and 5 questions were identification.

To work out a set of respondents within which the survey was carried out, a procedure of three-stage choice was chosen. As a basic set, a group of all organizations (registered units) having their seat in the Moravian-Silesian Region was chosen. In the first stage of the choice, a selective set of the size of 300 respondents from the basic set was worked out by the technique of quote choice; quotes had been made in such a way that in the selective choice a percentage representation of the organization's addressed groups according to the prevailing activities (branches) correspond with a percentage representation of specified prevailing activities (branches) in the basic set where needed data was obtained from the Moravian-Silesian Region Statistic Yearbook 2008. In the second stage of the choice the set of respondents was then worked out within particular quotas by the technique of random choice (by means of a generator of random numbers).

Covering letters including a reference to the questionnaire were distributed by e-mail on 4th September 2009, filled in questionnaires were then receiving from 5th September 2009 to 10th October 2009. Out of the total number of 300 (100 %) of sent questionnaires 37 (12.3 %) of them returned completed (6 organizations used talent management, 31 did not use it), 12 questionnaires (4 %) returned as undeliverable (dissolution of the organization, change of e-mail address and the like) and 251 questionnaires (83.7 %) did not return.

As a return of distributed questionnaires was relatively low (from the total number of 300 distributed questionnaires only 37 of them returned completed, which was 12.3 %). For the purpose of obtaining such a number of responses that would make the formulation of relevant conclusions possible, the author of the article decided to perform another round of a survey. In that second round an inquiring via telephone was chosen as a method of a survey, respondents were asked questions identical with the questions used in electronic inquiring.

Telephone inquiring took place from 16th up to 24th November 2009. Altogether, 300 identical respondents (100 %) were addressed as in the case of written inquiring with the result that with 37 respondents (12.3 %) who had completed electronic questionnaire the inquiring on the phone was not realized (after finding out that a respondent had already completed the electronic questionnaire a telephone call was finished), 200 respondents (66.7 %) answered questions of

telephone inquiring (3 of them used talent management, 197 did not use it) 39 respondents (13 %) did not answer the questions of telephone inquiring for the reason of being busy or for some other reasons it was not possible to get into a telephone contact with 24 respondents (8 %), (maximum of 3 attempts were made).

On the basis of both rounds realization, both written and by means of a telephone call it can be said that 237 respondents (79 %) answered questions included in the questionnaire and 63 respondents (21 %) did not answer them. The set of responses from 237 respondents (79 %) can be considered as meeting requirements for the formulation of relevant conclusions resulting from the evaluation of responses to questions in the questionnaire.

B.Data Processing

After checking all electronic questionnaires completeness and the completeness of recorded responses to all telephone inquiring, subsequent processing of obtained data was carried out from 26th November up to 8th December 2009.

Classification of the first grade was performed for questions concerning problems under solution. The results were processed in the form of frequency tables, a verbal description and a graphic representation. For questions of identification both classification of the first stage was performed during which the results were processed in the form of frequency tables, a verbal description and a graphic representation, and the classification of the second stage - the results were processed in the form of contingency tables.

VI. OUTCOMES

On the basis of processing the data obtained by applying a questionnaire survey aimed at the use of talent management by organizations in the Moravian-Silesian Region in which 237 respondents were involved it can be said that talent management is applied by organizations in the specified region to a small extent; this approach is used by 3.8 % of organization, that is 9 from 237 (100 %) of respondents who answered questions included in the questionnaire (see Table V). On the other hand, however, the use of talent management by a minimum number but at least some number of respondents shows that the specified approach is not completely unknown as it has been until recently.

From 9 organizations using the approach of talent management, 3 of them rank among medium (from 51 to 250 employees) and 6 of them rank among large (over 250 employees) organizations, they mostly (8 organizations) operate for a longer period (from 10 up to 15, and more than 15 years), their prevailing activity (branch) is manufacturing industry (3 organizations), civil engineering (2 organizations) and accommodation and catering (2 organizations). But there can be found also organizations performing other activities, operating in other industries (trade and repairs, activities in the field of real estate and renting; business activities). A majority of those organizations, 6 of them, started to use talent management in the horizon of the last 5 years, only in

one

TABLE V
USE OF TALENT MANAGEMENT

Has talent management been put into practice in your organization?	Absolute frequency (number of respondents)	Relative frequency (percentage representation)
yes	9	3.8 %
no	228	96.2 %
Total	237	100 %

Source: own processing

case the period of utilization of that approach is longer than 5 years and 2 organizations use talent management less than two years. As far as a legal form is concerned, in 6 cases these are commercial companies, the rest of 2 subjects are private entrepreneurs. Among organizations using talent management, cooperatives or state-owned companies are completely missing. A majority of those organizations, 7 of them, is owned by a foreign owner (a shareholder).

As a whole, these organizations evaluate the use of talent management as beneficial (6 organizations as very successful and beneficial, 3 organizations as partially successful and beneficial) not only for the organization as such but also for particular employees. All 9 organizations think talent management one of their priorities. As regards a practical application of theoretical knowledge, conditions of efficient working of that approach - talent management is in all 9 organizations initiated and supported by organization's management, in majority of organizations, in 7 of them, have a worked out strategy of talent management that is there linked with organization's business strategy. In all 9 organizations talent management is really seen as a systematic and complex implementation of all three processes of that approach - acquisition, development and retention of employees in the organization. Reactions of the involved people to the implementation and the use of talent management were positive in those organizations.

And how does the current economic crisis impact on organizations using talent management? Two thirds of respondents (6 organizations) mentioned that in their case the current economic crisis had no impact on the field of talent management use. They state that talent management is still considered a priority in their organizations, they consider this approach a key investment to the future or that their business activity has not been hit by the crisis so far. Remaining one third of organizations (2 organizations) are experiencing a certain impact of the current economic crisis on the use of talent management - a certain review of the purposefulness of the present system of talent management costs is being taken place or the budget intended for talent management has even been cut (or some its parts, for example the one intended for development and education). In comparison with the study *'The War on Talent? Talent Management under Threat in Uncertain Times'* which was worked out by the CIPD organization in November 2008 among 705 respondents -

CIPD members, executives in organizations working both in a public and private sector, in profit and non-profit organizations we can say that the findings obtained on the basis of a questionnaire survey in organizations of the Moravian-Silesian Region are relevant to the conclusions published in the mentioned study - there are both organizations that do not experience the impact of the crisis, they still consider talent management a priority and key investment in the future, and organizations that have experienced the impact of the crisis on their working, which reflected mainly in reassessing the purposefulness of the existing system of talent management costs or directly in cut in the budget for the whole talent management or at least its part [22].

From 228 organizations that do not use talent management, 195 of them are small (up to 50 employees), 19 are medium (from 51 to 250 employees) and 14 are large (over 250 employees) organizations. They operating for various time, from a period of less than 2 years (2 organizations) up to more than 15 years (96 organizations), their prevailing activity (branch) is commerce; repairs of motor vehicles and products for personal consumption and mostly for households (88 organizations). We can see there, however, organizations performing other activities, operating in other branch (activities in the area of real estates and renting; business activities, civil engineering, public, social and personal services, manufacturing industry and others). These organizations in most cases (215 organizations) do not have a foreign owner (shareholder). As for legal status of organizations that do not use talent management we can find there all four types - trading companies (176 organizations), private entrepreneurs (41 organizations), 2 cooperatives and 9 state companies; commercial companies, however, prevail.

As the main reason why organizations do not use talent management they state that they are not familiar with it; this reason was mentioned in 118 of 228 organizations not using talent management, which can be understood as a negative finding. In case organizations are familiar with talent management then they consider as an essential reason why they do not use it lack of sources necessary for talent management application, both financial (36 organizations) and personnel (33 organizations). Some respondents think that the specified approach is too demanding as regards their organization (23 organizations) or unsuitable for it (10 organizations), other organizations (8 organizations) mention as a reason why they do not use talent management a small size of their organization, its short history or low confidence in talent management as a new approach (see Table VI).

Also realization of testing a dependency between using and not using of talent management and certain factors determining this situation was part of processing the data obtained by the survey. It has been found out that there is a dependency between using and not using of talent management and activities being performed in the field of career development, the existence of foreign owner (shareholder) and the actual number of employees; but

between using and not using of talent management and

TABLE VI
REASONS WHY ORGANIZATIONS DO NOT USE TALENT MANAGEMENT

For what reason you do not use talent management in your organization?	Absolute frequency (number of respondents)	Relative frequency (percentage representation)
we are not familiar with it	118	51.8 %
we are familiar with it, but it seems to us to be too demanding in terms of organizational work	23	10.1 %
we are familiar with it, but we have not to our disposal resources - personnel	33	14.4 %
we are familiar with it, but we have not to our disposal means - financial	36	15.8 %
we are familiar with it, but we do not consider it as suitable	10	4.4 %
other reason	8	3.5 %
Total	228	100 %

Source: own processing

a prevailing activity in the organization, organization's legal standard and the period of organization's working does not exist any dependency.

Within processing the obtained data also testing of hypothesis formulated at the beginning of the survey was performed. Hypothesis A, assuming that less than 10 % of organizations in the Moravian-Silesian Region use talent management was confirmed. Also hypothesis B assuming than the main reason why talent management is not used because it was not known has been confirmed.

VII. DISCUSSION

By the survey it has been found out that a prevailing activity (branch) is not the factor that influences whether talent management is used or not, because a majority of activities the organizations are dealing with and use talent management can be also found in organizations that do not use it. It is similar with organizations in case of organization's legal form because both among organizations using talent management and among those that do not apply it, a majority of subjects are commercial companies. What is interesting is the fact that among organizations that do not use talent management there are either cooperatives or state-owned companies. On the contrary, among organizations that do not use talent management, organizations of all four legal forms can be found. Even a longer period of organization's working does not influence whether they use talent management or not because organizations whose period of working is from 10 up to 15 and more years can be found in both groups of respondents, both those who use talent management and those who do not apply this approach. It does not hold true that the longer the organization works the more probably is that it will

use talent management. Apparently, the truth is that organizations that use talent management first had to build up a certain position on the market during a certain period and then also maintain it, gain stability, competitiveness, be financially strong it means to have sufficient sources and only then decide for the use of talent management. Also such organizations, however, do not have to use talent management necessarily it always depends on organization's concrete situation.

According to the author the most essential factor influencing whether talent management is used or not is the existence of a foreign owner (shareholder) - a majority of organizations using it have got a foreign owner (shareholder). By this fact it can be partly explained why these organizations use talent management - their foreign owner or a shareholder transmits the approach used in organizations of their own countries to the Czech environment, the approach the contributions of which have been confirmed by a practical use and there is not any reason why it should not work under certain circumstances also in our business environment. This fact can be confirmed by a finding that in a majority of cases the organizations that have not got a foreign owner (shareholder) do not use talent management. Another factor influencing whether talent management is used or it is not is a number of employees in the organization, its size. All organizations using talent management can be ranked to medium ones (from 51 to 250 employees) and bigger (over 250 employees); among organizations that do not use talent management we can find small or medium as well as big organizations, a majority of those respondents, however, falls to the category of small organizations (up to 50 employees).

On the basis of summarization and systematization of talent management knowledge, the evaluation of this approach drawbacks and benefits, getting acquainted with the practice abroad, and the evaluation of questionnaire survey data obtained in Moravian-Silesian Region organizations it can be recommended to those who use that approach (not only in this region but generally in the whole Czech Republic) to continue their activity and in case of certain drawbacks to improve their approach and act as an example of the successful application in the Czech practice and to those who do not use talent management to start using this valuable, beneficial and by foreign practice as well by a number of studies verified approach (of course, relevant to organization's concrete situation).

Since the ignorance of talent management has been identified as a main cause of why it is not used, it is necessary to try to ensure the existence of a sufficient amount of quality and reliable information (awareness) on every aspect of talent management. Chances of how to ensure keeping people informed in the required quality and quantity is available, it is only a question of their practical application. It concerns, for example, ensuring a higher level of information on the existence of the specified approach as such, on its advantages and benefits, positive experience in its application and possibilities of the specified approach in every field of

activities, various types of organizations (with the introduction of the existence of certain limits in the approach feasibility taking into account a size of the organization) or on a possibility of its use for various groups of employees (all employees, managers and specialists, managers only, specialists only). In some organizations it would be desired to change a quality of human resources management, to adjust standards of work in the specified field and to try to change a point of view of organization's priorities arrangement towards awareness and taking into account a significant position of human resources management, and thus also the importance of talent management.

A common denominator of all above-mentioned recommendations in the field of a sufficient number of information is a necessity of talent management massive promotion by means of all available instruments. This includes both publishing of professional papers, conference papers or monographs dealing with the specified topic, and giving lectures, organizing seminars, workshops for experts with practical experience. Also including the issue of talent management into curricula of followed master and doctoral study of relevant fields or into MBA study curricula as well as personal promotion of talent management by the representations of organizations successfully using that approach or the involvement of professional associations, e.g. the Club of Czech Republic Personnel Officers and others would be a considerable contribution.

Another cause why talent management is not used in organizations of the Moravian-Silesian Region having been confirmed by the questionnaire survey of talent management, is the fear of a certain organizational as well as time demanding activity. This 'fear' often causes that in the end the organizations will not apply talent management in spite of making decision on the implementation of this approach in case they have a sufficient amount of financial and other means and also further prerequisites of the implementation and utilization are met.

By the author suggested methodology of the introduction and utilization of talent management in the organization might serve as a certain instrument or instructions for practical materialization of that approach. The form of the methodology is based on the structure of a talent management thoughts map (see Appendix). Its particular steps "copy" the logical sequence of partial areas and sub-areas of that approach as well as their particular activities. The methodology has been designed so that its contents and form could serve the organization making a decision on talent management implementation and utilization as a sort of certain guideline and an aid enabling it to perform particular activities of that procedure. As a result, it will contribute to the successful materialization of that comprehensive and systematic approach to work with talented persons.

It stands to reason that a concrete form of talent management application i.e. concrete performing of particular and in the methodology described activities, their sequence, continuity and etc. will always depend on the organization's

specific situation. It means it will depend on the level of human resources management, on the amount of available sources, on the approach and involvement of not only organization's management but also of all its employees, and on its current condition and the like.

A similar situation arises in case a time period of performing particular activities or a horizon of comprehensive implementation of talent management in the organization are limited - it is not possible exactly to determine either the first or second. As far as the time of receiving contributions resulting from the appropriate implementation and utilization of talent management in the organization is concerned, on the basis of practical experience of organizations using that approach it is obvious that sometimes it may be a horizon of several years. However, even under such conditions the application of talent management will pay off as it follows from information provided by those organizations. That is why the organizations that do not use talent management should certainly think about using that approach. By practice confirmed contributions resulting from the use of talent management may serve as a sufficient motivation for the implementation and wider application of that systematic and comprehensive approach to work with talented individuals in Czech organizations.

VIII. CONCLUSION

More and more quick and frequent changes of the external environment make higher and higher demands on organizations. For almost all types of organizations the main asset to manage those changes are people. Without a skilled workforce, without employees equipped by required abilities and knowledge, a number of organizations will not be able not only to keep up with competition but they even may not to survive under specified conditions.

Talent management can be considered as one of fundamental instruments of human resources management in the organization. But what should be the organization's attitude to the management of its talented employees? It should offer them a real perspective and pay attention to the strategy of their management. Not to use only formal programs of talent development and concentrate on career management and succession planning but to apply a comprehensive system of talent management that will enable those talented individuals a real development and a deeper identification with the organization. This system then helps organizations acquire and retain highly talented employees, build on their strengths, reward their success, provide them with opportunities for advancement and increase their overall efficiency and thus the efficiency of the whole organization.

Also this article was concerned with a possibility of using the system of talent management for human resources management in the organization. Its aim was to describe not only the substance, significance, contributions and particular processes of that approach but mainly to bring information on the contents and the level of how talent management is used

by organizations in the Moravian-Silesian Region.

After the introduction concerned with a wider context of the topic being solved and article's goal definition, the basic concepts were explained in another part of the text - talent and talent management. In addition to pointing out to certain disunity in understanding those concepts not only a prevailing view of these issues in the Czech Republic was mentioned there but also the opinion of article's author on talent and talent management definitions. In another part of the article the significance was mentioned as well as actual contributions resulting from the use of talent management in practice. Especially processes of talent management - acquisition, development and retention of talents as a concrete instrument of systematic work with individuals in the organization were thoroughly described. The text characterizes particular parts of the given system in detail and it offers instructions, concrete instruments how to put into effect partial activities within the acquisition, development and retention of talents in such way that these activities really lead to a survival and growth, to outperforming the current competition, and to a considerable increase in organization's added value.

The last part of the article provided information on the extent to which talent management is used by organizations of the Moravian-Silesian Region, namely on the basis of data obtained from a questionnaire survey. The method of research, the shape of questionnaire, the way of choosing respondents, timing of research materialization as well as the way of obtained data evaluation were specified there. Also the outcomes of processing the data drawn from the survey were verbally and partly also graphically represented there. Organizations using talent management as well as organizations that do not apply it were characterized in the article (by means of data about a size, the length of operating, the field of activity, the existence or non-existence of a foreign owner - shareholder, and a legal status). It has been found out that the level of using talent management by organizations in this region is really low as the author assumed in the introductory part of the article; only 3.8 % of the approached respondents apply this method. As the main reason why talent management is not used was identified the fact that organizations did not know it. Within processing the obtained data also testing of hypothesis formulated at the beginning of the survey was carried out. A prerequisite that less than 10 % of organizations in the Moravian-Silesian Region use talent management has been confirmed as well as a prerequisite that the main reason why it is not used in organizations of this region is their unfamiliarity with it.

The contents of another part was considering respective factors that influence or do not influence the use of talent management; the existence or nonexistence of a foreign owner (shareholder) was identified as the most essential factor. The size of the organization is considered as another factor substantially influencing the situation in the field, whether talent management is used or not.

As a conclusion, recommendations for a broader application of this approach in the Czech practice were given including

acquainting with by the author suggested methodology of the introduction and application of talent management in the organization based on a talent management thoughts map which is graphically represented in the enclosure to this article.

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APPENDIX A THOUGHTS MAP OF TALENT MANAGEMENT IN THE ORGANIZATION

